

THE NEED FOR MOTIVATIONAL DEVELOPMENT OF FUTURE PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS KNOWLEDGE OF SPORT TOURISM

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11366725>

Abstract: In this article, the theoretical-methodological foundations of the motivational development of future physical education teachers' knowledge of tourism are studied, in particular, its necessity. It was also analyzed that the motive and motivation system fulfills the function of internal regulation of a person's activity, behavior, behavior and is the main factor in being able to satisfy needs, desires, good intentions, wishes, ideals, conscience, and goals.

Key words: physical education, sport, tourism, sports tourism, professional activity, training, component, empirical, pedagogical feature, methodology.

INTRODUCTION. Motive is a factor that causes the fulfillment of a certain goal in human activity, vaj. Motive is an internal impulse that urges a person to action and activity, appearing as a high form of need. It includes need and instinct, inclination and emotion, ideal and other motives. In modern psychology, the term motive is used to express various events and situations that activate the subject. A set of motives for behavior and activity is called motivation. Therefore, in improving the training system of future physical education teachers, it is necessary to pay attention to the formation of motives for their professional development, to develop an innovative methodology.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS. Many studies have been conducted on the development of the professional skills of physical education and sports specialists, and the effective organization of the formation of moral values in athletes. aspects of mental, functional preparation; N.N. Tokhtaboyev, A.N. Shopulatov, S.S. Tajibayev, F. Kerimov, R. Abdumalikov, A. Muzaffarov, A. Mirzayev, A. Khudoyorov conducted research on improving the training of sports specialists using action games.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. Motivation is the process of movement of motives, a set of motives that urge a person to the main activity. Motiv, when translated from French, means force, cause.

E. Ghaziyev and R. Asomova's motive and motivation system fulfills the function of internal regulation of a person's activity, behavior, and behavior, satisfying his needs, desire, good intention, wish, inclination, feeling, ideal, who

determined that faith, conscience, ability to set goals, etc., are the main factors of practical realization [2]. According to the Russian scientist A.N. Leontyev, the motivational environment of a person is a whole system that develops throughout his life. It is considered to be mobile with its own hierarchy, it shows the subject of needs and the state of the individual. Therefore, there are various needs under the human consciousness, which means that these needs become motivation that shapes human behavior and external activity [4].

In our opinion, the motive arises and is formed on the basis of need. Stabilization of need ensures effective formation of motivation. Since action is the composition of activity, it is controlled by the purpose and motive of activity. Sometimes the concept of "motive" is replaced by the terms "emotion", "goal", "setting". Sometimes it is characterized by the concepts of motivation, instigator, exhortation [6]. That is why future teachers of social education need to set their professional career in the right direction, to develop an inner urge to achieve success, and to guide them on this basis.

In Western psychology, two types of motivation and their characteristics have been studied in depth. These are extrinsic (depends on external conditions and situations) and intrinsic (appears in connection with personal dispositions - needs, attitudes, interests, inclinations, desires) motivations. Discussions in this direction are reflected in H. Heckhausen's book "Motivation and activity".

H. Heckhausen develops the principles of motivation. According to the first principle, intrinsically motivated behavior is not aimed at satisfying physical needs, such as hunger, thirst, and avoiding pain. According to scientists, the work carried out in this direction has revealed that these needs do not serve to restore the homeostasis broken by the body. However, in external behavior, they can be corrected, and motivated behavior is interpreted as aimless activity.

Y. Klinger calls game activity an aimless directed action based on interactive motivation. According to R. White, the greatest activities of an individual in the process of interaction with the environment are called mobility motivation. American scientist Mark Rujnes agrees with this opinion and considers the initial stages of activity to be intensive, and the stages close to the result to be extensive.

The factor of motivation to achieve success in professional activity is of great importance in forming motivation for extreme sports among future physical education teachers. At the beginning of the last century, D.S. McClelland developed the Thematic Apperceptive Test (TAT) methodology aimed at determining the differences in the occurrence of individual quality changes of

success motivation. He identified two types of success motivation: motivation to achieve success and motivation to avoid failure. Later, this method was modified by H. Heckhausen, W. Mayer, L. Kemmler. H. Heckhausen defines the nature of interdependence of active activity and success motivation at the most important level and shows three important motivational vectors:

1. Individual subjective perception of the probability of success and difficulty of the task before the individual;
2. The level of importance of the task for the subject, as well as the strength of the desire to support and increase self-esteem;
3. A person's tendency to adequately attribute responsibility for success and failure to himself, other people and the situation [8]. Therefore, the role of these vectors in creating motivation for sports tourism among future physical education teachers is considered high. Identifying psychological factors and developing the pedagogical basis of their solution are urgent tasks for today's higher education.

Within the framework of the dissertation, it is necessary to take into account their activity and educational stress when directing future physical education teachers to motivational activities based on innovative approaches.

According to P. Fress and J. Piaget, it is necessary to have sufficient motivation to carry out the activity. However, if the motivation is too high, the level of activity and tension increases, and this in turn causes the deterioration of the performance of the activity and behavior. From this point of view, an extremely high level of motivation can cause negative emotional effects: stress, excitement, tension, which can lead to negative situations in the activity. It can be seen that a very high level of motivation is not always the best aspect [9].

D. McClelland explains that achievement motivation can also develop during adulthood as a result of learning. It shows the following traits that show success motivation in people:

- prioritization of activities under conditions of maximum success motivation, i.e. performing tasks at an average level;
- success motivation does not always lead to high results. Also, high scores are not always considered the result of the activation of achievement motivation;
- the responsibility to take personal responsibility in the implementation of some activity. There are situations and conditions where the level of risk is clear or moderate, and chance does not play a role in achieving success.

- prefers to express sufficient opinion about the results achieved in his work;

- since a person is eager for new things, he tries to find new, effective ways to perform tasks [5]. Therefore, it is one of the urgent tasks to form the ability to properly balance the desire, need and personal responsibility of future physical education teachers to achieve success in innovative motivational activities.

Y.M. Rozhkov motivation is overcoming a difficulty, overcoming difficulties through control and organization with people or ideas. Regardless of how it can be done, it is to do it independently very quickly, Debt says. He believes that overcoming obstacles and achieving high results leads to a person's self-expression, competition with others, and increased self-esteem through the successful use of their abilities [7]. Therefore, motivation for future physical education teachers is based on the desire to achieve good results in their professional activities, social demand and need.

According to H. Heckhausen, motivation is a psychodynamic system of a person, which determines the vital attitude of a person to the external environment and controls, directs, and organizes his activities. The nature and dynamics of motivation is caused by a number of factors. Psychic processes are situational, voluntary, emotional, directly related to the structure of the person (need, orientation, value orientation), a person's attitude to the outside world, personal activity, planning of results, predetermination. Therefore, preparing future physical education teachers for innovative pedagogical activities, improving physical education, motivation and other factors in their work efficiency, voluntary, emotional, attitude to the outside world, personal activity, planning of results as well position is high.

The results of the analysis of the available scientific and methodical literature testify that in recent years the number of students with different levels of physical fitness is increasing. is happening It is difficult for students of this type to carry out training programs created within the framework of training regimes (in accordance with physiologically based standards for given age groups). This situation is related to the discrepancy between the physical fitness of a significant number of students and the normative tests performed by them. It was observed that students need to strengthen the necessary motivation for physical training, to ensure their active participation in practical training, to perform physical loads, as well as to show determination in achieving the required result for the optimal functioning of all systems of the body. Activation of physical activity of such students remains an important issue. The

methodology of the process of teaching these students and its organization is considered to have its own characteristics. This situation leads to the need to develop a new methodology for teaching movement situations to students with different levels of physical development and physical training. In recent years, new innovative processes have been widely applied to the education system. At the same time, innovations are expressed in the integration of initiatives in the educational process and the introduction of innovations, and together they lead to large or small global changes. In a number of studies, it was found that in the teaching of physical culture and sports sciences in higher education institutions, insufficient attention is paid to the training process using new innovative, technological tools. There is a principled contradiction between the model system of teacher training and his individual, creative activity" [3]. The development of new methods and approaches to the organization of the educational process, which offers and encourages the increasing activity of students in the acquisition of professional knowledge, qualifications and skills, is crucial in improving the system of training specialists in the field of physical culture education.

It is necessary for future physical education teachers to have professional communication skills, to be educated physically and mentally, and to have the ability to attract students to sports in the future. Sports and aesthetics, sports and ethics, sports and communication, sports and culture, sports culture and personal development - pedagogical culture in practice - understanding, understanding and integration of communication of the future physical culture teacher complement each other and are inseparable concepts. In the process of forming a future physical culture teacher, it is especially important that the beauty in sports, i.e., its appearance, body shape, the fact that it arouses great pleasure in pedagogical activities, leaves deep impressions and evokes unforgettable emotions. .

According to Sh.Abdullayeva and E.Khurramov, "in physical education classes, the teacher aims to develop people who are mature in every way: trained, clear-minded, brave, persistent, determined, who can protect the Motherland in the future." . From this point of view, innovative organization of activities of future physical education teachers, updating and enrichment of educational content is of great importance. Along with the development of the educational process, the urgent issue facing today's requirements is to prepare future physical education teachers for innovative activities in theoretical and practical terms, to achieve efficiency in the physical education of the young

generation. Only a physically fit and healthy person will have the opportunity to fully express his intellectual and spiritual potential" [1]. Therefore, improving the training system of future physical education teachers and directing them to innovative activities remains one of the priority tasks.

In this sense, the comparative-analytical study of the historical experiences of the physical education system in our country, the generalization of practical experiences based on the critical observation, the correct organization of the innovative activities of physical education teachers, and the determination of its prospective strategy. For this, there is a need to carry out targeted pedagogical research. Teaching the content of physical education to future physical education teachers on a scientific basis, modernizing its organizational and technological foundations, developing future development trends is one of the urgent issues facing the science of pedagogy.

CONCLUSION. In conclusion, the role of the motivational approach in education in the training of future teachers is high and its effectiveness is high. Because the motivational approach directs students to their professional activities by forming a motivational attitude based on their needs and interests. This increases the desire of future teachers to achieve professional success, acquire professional knowledge and skills, and improve them. Including, the preparation of future physical education teachers for professional activity based on a motivational approach shows its effectiveness.

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